

PI3K/Akt in IPF: Untangling Fibrosis and Charting Therapies

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Abstract

Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) is a chronic, progressive lung disease characterized by abnormal epithelial repair, persistent inflammation, and excessive extracellular matrix deposition, leading to irreversible scarring and respiratory failure. Central to its pathogenesis is the dysregulation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, which drives fibroblast activation, epithelial-mesenchymal transition, apoptosis resistance, and cellular senescence. Senescent cells contribute to fibrosis through the secretion of pro-inflammatory and profibrotic factors in the senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP). Current antifibrotic therapies, Nintedanib and Pirfenidone, only slow disease progression and are limited by side effects, highlighting the need for novel treatments. This review focuses on the role of PI3K/Akt signaling in IPF pathogenesis, its intersection with inflammation and fibrosis, and emerging therapeutic approaches targeting molecules along this pathway.

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1 Introduction

Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) is a chronic, progressive fibrosing interstitial pneumonia of unknown origin, characterized by a progressively worsening dyspnea and declining lung function (Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis Clinical Research Network et al., 2012; Raghu et al., 2011). It is a fatal age-related disorder, predominantly occurring in males, with a median survival age of 2-5 years after diagnosis (Moss et al., 2022; Spagnolo et al., 2021). Although considered rare, existing data indicates that the global occurrence of IPF rivals several cancer types, including stomach, liver, testicular, and cervical cancers (Hutchinson et al., 2015), with approximately 40,000 new cases diagnosed annually in Europe alone (Leslie, 2012), and its incidence doubling with each successive decade after the age of 50. The fatality of the disease, combined with its increasing prevalence and the subsequent strain on healthcare resources, highlights the urgency of addressing IPF treatment.

Historically, IPF was understood to be an inflammation driven disease that eventually progressed to fibrosis. However, this concept was challenged by two pivotal clinical trials. The first, INSPIRE, found that patients treated with Interferon- γ did not experience significant clinical benefits. The second, PANTHER, evaluated a combination of three immunosuppressive agents (prednisone, azathioprine, and N-acetylcysteine) and revealed increased risks of death and hospitalization compared to placebo. (Behr, 2012; Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis Clinical Research Network et al., 2012). These trials marked a paradigm shift in our understanding of IPF, suggesting that fibrosis, rather than inflammation, is central to IPF pathophysiology. Fibrosis in IPF is characterized by fibroblast activation, excessive collagen deposition, leading to the distortion of lung architecture and impaired gas exchange (Figure 1). This fibrotic process is driven by the aberrant activation of fibroblasts and myofibroblasts, which secrete collagen and other extracellular matrix proteins, resulting in the thickening and stiffening of the lung

tissue. In the context of these findings, two antifibrotic therapies, Nintedanib and Pirfenidone, have been developed and approved for the treatment of IPF (Galli et al., 2017; Richeldi et al., 2014). However, these drugs only slow down disease progression (King et al., 2014) and up to 40% patients discontinue treatment citing gastrointestinal, dermatological or liver-associated adverse drug reactions (Ogura et al., 2023). Hence, lung transplantation remains the last resort for IPF patients, which is impractical for a majority of cases, considering factors such as age and comorbidities (Spagnolo et al., 2021)

At a molecular level, the transition from inflammation to fibrosis as the focus of IPF research was further substantiated by studies that identified key signaling pathways involved in fibrogenesis (Kulkarni et al., 2016). Among these, the PI3K/Akt pathway is involved in vital cellular processes such as survival, growth, proliferation, metabolism, apoptosis and angiogenesis. PI3Ks are lipid kinases divided into three classes – Class I, Class II and Class III. In mammalian cells, Class I PI3K catalytic subunits catalyze the phosphorylation of PtdIns-4,5-P₂ (PIP₂) to generate PtdIns-3,4,5-P₃ (PIP₃). Upon phosphorylation, PIP₃ recruits two pleckstrin homology domain-containing kinases: the serine threonine kinase, Akt, and phosphoinositide-dependent kinase 1 (PDK-1). Akt undergoes conformational changes on direct binding to PIP₃, exposing two of its amino acid sites, serine 473 and threonine 308, for phosphorylation by mammalian target of rapamycin complex 2 (mTORC2) and PDK1, respectively (Martini et al., 2014; Sarris et al., 2012). Once fully activated, Akt readily phosphorylates its downstream effectors such as mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR), nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), and p70 ribosomal protein S6 kinase (p70S6K), contributing to various cellular processes. PI3K/Akt signaling mediates key cellular functions such as proliferation and survival, bridging the mechanistic overlap between tumorigenesis and fibrotic progression of IPF. Understanding its regulation and potential for therapeutic targeting is critical to advancing IPF research and treatment strategies. Therefore, this review focuses on the role of the PI3K/Akt pathway in IPF pathogenesis, examining its multifaceted interactions and elucidating how dysregulation within this signaling axis contributes to the progression of fibrotic lung disease. Additionally, the review explores existing and emerging therapeutic avenues targeting key molecules along the PI3K pathway, discussing novel exploratory strategies for IPF treatment.

Figure 1. Pathophysiological mechanisms underlying Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis.

2 The PI3K/Akt Signaling Pathway: Senescence, Fibrosis and the PI3K Signaling Nexus

The PI3K/Akt signaling axis drives cellular senescence (Gulluni et al., 2021; Schafer et al., 2017), linking hallmark features of aging—such as telomere attrition, mitochondrial dysfunction, and impaired autophagy—to the molecular pathways underlying IPF pathogenesis. The association between IPF and aging is evidenced by the characteristic features of aging that are also observed in IPF, including impaired autophagy, DNA damage, mitochondrial dysfunction and telomere attrition. Telomere shortening triggers senescence, and is also an important risk factor for IPF, particularly familial IPF (Alder et al., 2008). Mutations in hTERT or hTR result in shorter telomeres and this telomere attrition in murine alveolar epithelial type 2 cells (AEC), but not mesenchymal cells, has been shown to promote fibrosis (Armanios, 2012; Armanios et al., 2007). Lung fibroblasts from IPF patients also exhibit a senescent phenotype characterized by shorter telomeres and mitochondrial dysfunction (Álvarez et al., 2017). However, cellular senescence typically serves as a protective mechanism by limiting excessive cell proliferation, hence its role in promoting fibrosis in IPF appears paradoxical. Studies have shed light on the mechanisms through which senescence contributes to fibrosis. (Hashimoto et al., 2016; Schafer et al., 2017). Telomere shortening exacerbates AEC dysfunction, while mitochondrial impairment and increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) drive the activation of pathways such as PI3K/mTOR. In the context of aging and IPF, reduced or lost PTEN expression induces Akt-dependent alveolar epithelial senescence (Qiu et al., 2019). Akt hyperactivation drives apoptosis resistance and mTOR activity leads to inhibition of autophagy, factors which are necessary for fibrogenesis (Romero et al., 2016). This process leads to the upregulation of senescence markers including senescence-associated β -galactosidase, p21, p16, and p53, along with the emergence of a senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP). SASP is characterized by the secretion of pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic cytokines, including interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-8 (IL-8), and TGF- β (Papiris et al., 2018).

The emergence of SASP, driven by upregulated senescence markers, has been closely linked to PTEN loss and Akt hyperactivation to senescence, as demonstrated in bleomycin-induced models where Akt2 knockdown mitigated the senescence phenotype (Qiu et al., 2019). In IPF, AEC are particularly prone to this senescent phenotype due to persistent PI3K/Akt activation in the absence of adequate PTEN function (Minagawa et al., 2011; Qiu et al., 2019; Yao et al., 2021). Although SASP production occurs in both fibroblasts and AECs, it is the SASP from AECs that appears to be critical for the progression of fibrosis. This dysfunctional feedback loop of senescence, SASP production, PI3K signaling mediated fibroproliferation and apoptosis resistance, ultimately accelerates fibrosis, making the PI3K/Akt axis a critical target for therapeutic intervention in IPF by addressing the underlying mechanisms of senescence and fibrosis (Alder et al., 2008; Tu et al., 2023; Yao et al., 2021).

2.2 The effectors upstream of PI3K/Akt and their roles in IPF

Upstream and downstream effectors of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway drive IPF progression, mediating the interplay between pro-fibrotic stimuli and cellular responses. Upstream, growth factors and cytokines such as TGF- β , PDGF, and VEGF aberrantly activate the pathway, driving processes like fibroblast proliferation and extracellular matrix production. Downstream, PI3K/Akt signaling regulates key effector mechanisms, including myofibroblast differentiation, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), and metabolic reprogramming, which together perpetuate the fibrotic environment. Understanding these interactions reveals how dysregulated PI3K signaling orchestrates IPF pathogenesis.

In IPF, damaged alveolar epithelial cells, alveolar macrophages and fibroblasts release profibrotic cytokines such as TGF- β , Platelet-Derived growth factor (PDGF), Connective Tissue Growth Factor (CTGF) Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), and fibroblast growth factor (FGF) which aberrantly stimulate the PI3K/Akt pathway (Bakin et al., 2000; Schaefer et al., 2011; Wilkes et al., 2005), hence perpetuating the cycle of injury and dysregulated repair. PDGF, a key target of Nintedanib, plays a critical role in stimulating fibroblast proliferation and collagen deposition via the PI3K/Akt pathway

(Wollin et al., 2014). TGF- β is the primary orchestrator of lung fibrosis, driving fibroblast activation, differentiation, and Extra Cellular Matrix (ECM) deposition. TGF- β also activates CTGF expression by primary AECs (Yang et al., 2014), which further stimulates EMT and upregulates ECM deposition. CTGF in turn induces activation of TGF- β as well as VEGF in a positive feedback loop (Lipson et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2014). This loop can be broken by CTGF inhibition, but CTGF expression by type 2 AECs and active fibroblasts is more prominent in the early stages of fibrosis and reduced in the later stages (Pan et al., 2001). This could explain why a phase 3 study of a CTGF inhibitor, Pamrevlumab, showed no clinical benefits compared to placebo (Raghu et al., 2024). Apart from its direct effect on CTGF, TGF- β , increases hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α (HIF-1 α) expression via Smad signaling, thereby upregulating VEGF gene expression (Epstein Shochet et al., 2021; McMahon et al., 2006). Akt activation also induces the upregulation of HIF-1 α expression, which subsequently increases VEGF levels, promoting angiogenesis (Lu et al., 2010). Growth factors play a complex and sometimes isoform-specific role in fibrosis, with certain variants promoting fibrotic responses while others exhibit antifibrotic properties. For instance, VEGF165b has been shown to inhibit fibrosis, in contrast to VEGF165a, which promotes fibrotic processes (Atamas, 2017; Barratt et al., 2017), implying that a more isoform-specific approach is required to yield substantial clinical benefits. Similarly, FGF was traditionally considered profibrotic, but newer findings suggest a preventative and therapeutic role. FGF1 attenuates TGF- β 1 induced fibrosis by decreasing e-cadherin expression and inhibiting myofibroblast differentiation (Shimbori et al., 2016), FGF2 suppresses collagen production and fibroblast differentiation (Koo et al., 2018) while FGF7 and 10 improve lung repair and prolong survival in mouse models (MacKenzie et al., 2015).

Growth factor activation of PI3K promotes cell survival, but PTEN counterbalances it by dephosphorylating PIP3 to inhibit Akt (Cantley, 2002). Myofibroblasts extracted from IPF biopsies show reduced PTEN expression alongside Akt upregulation, and in bleomycin-induced mouse models, PTEN deficiency has been shown to exacerbate fibrosis, resulting in a 55% increase in collagen content compared to wild-type mice (White et al., 2006; Xia et al., 2008). PTEN suppression and aberrant activation of Akt can result in decreased autophagic activity, creating an environment that promotes fibroblast proliferation and apoptosis resistance. When IPF fibroblasts interact with type I collagen—a major component of the ECM in fibrotic tissues—Akt activity remains high while autophagy markers, such as LC3-II, are suppressed (Nho and Hergert, 2014; Patel et al., 2012; Yue et al., 2022).

2.3 The effectors downstream of PI3K/Akt and their roles in IPF

The PI3K/Akt pathway promotes persistent fibrotic foci by driving apoptosis resistance and fibroblast proliferation (Wan et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2019). Akt phosphorylates and inactivates FOXO3a, disrupting its role in apoptosis regulation and enabling unchecked fibroblast survival and proliferation. FOXO3a inhibition contributes to the accumulation of activated fibroblasts and their transition to myofibroblasts, which drive fibrosis (Nho et al., 2013).

Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT), another key fibrotic feature, involves the loss of epithelial markers like E-cadherin and upregulation of mesenchymal markers such as α -SMA, vimentin, and fibronectin (Gonzalez and Medici, 2014). Akt promotes EMT by activating transcription factors like Snail, ZEB1/2, Twist, and LEF-1, which repress E-cadherin and induce mesenchymal marker expression (Julien et al., 2007). Akt also phosphorylates GSK3- β , preventing β -catenin degradation. This stabilizes and translocates β -catenin to the nucleus, driving EMT-associated gene transcription (Zheng et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2004). In vivo, Akt1 $^{-/-}$ mice show resistance to hypoxia-induced pulmonary fibrosis, directly linking Akt inhibition to reduced fibroblast activity and apoptosis resistance (Abdalla et al., 2015).

3 PI3K/Akt Signaling Based Strategies to Treat IPF

Over the past two decades, extensive clinical trials have aimed to identify effective treatments for IPF. However, most investigational therapies have failed to demonstrate significant efficacy, highlighting the complex and challenging nature of this disease (Raghu, 2017; Zamora et al., 2024). This challenge arises in part from the poorly understood mechanisms driving IPF progression and the difficulty of reversing established fibrosis. Current approved therapies, pirfenidone and nintedanib, offer some benefit in slowing disease progression but are far from optimal in halting or reversing the fibrotic processes.

3.1 Commonalities between lung cancer and IPF

IPF and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) share molecular, cellular, and genetic similarities, including mutations in genes like p53, KRAS, and p21. Shared genetic predispositions, such as mutations in SFTPA1 and SFTPA2, lead to endoplasmic reticulum stress, impaired protein secretion, and apoptosis, driving fibrosis in IPF and tumorigenesis in lung cancer. Both diseases exhibit epigenetic changes, such as deregulated noncoding RNAs like miR-21, and involve common processes like EMT and apoptosis resistance. Abnormal activation of pathways like Wnt/ β -catenin and PI3K/Akt further contributes to metaplasia, hyperproliferation, fibrosis, and tumor growth (Rabinovich et al., 2012; Tzouveleki et al., 2019; Vancheri, 2013). The PI3K/Akt pathway is central to both diseases, promoting cell survival, proliferation, and resistance to apoptosis in NSCLC, and driving fibroblast proliferation, ECM deposition, and apoptosis resistance in IPF. Its influence on EMT, a shared process in fibrosis and cancer, facilitates epithelial marker loss and mesenchymal trait acquisition, fueling fibrosis and tumor invasion.

Despite these overlaps, IPF differs from cancer as it lacks monoclonality and metastatic potential. Cancer often begins in one organ and spreads, while IPF is a bilateral disease from early stages (Cool et al., 2006; Vancheri et al., 2010). These differences necessitate tailored treatment strategies for IPF. Drugs like Nintedanib, originally developed for cancer, target pathways common to fibrosis and tumorigenesis, slowing disease progression in both NSCLC and IPF. Similarly, Pirfenidone inhibits EMT and tumor stroma, addressing fibrosis and cancer metastasis. However, both treatments have dose-limiting toxicities, highlighting the urgent need for new therapies in IPF.

3.2 PI3K/Akt/mTOR Inhibitors to target IPF

Based on the overlapping metabolic profiles of IPF and lung cancer, Omipalisib was the first PI3K/mTOR inhibitor originally developed for solid tumors, and later repurposed for IPF. Pharmacokinetic studies with Omipalisib showed a decrease in glucose uptake and an acceptable tolerability profile; however, patients also experienced adverse events like gastrointestinal disturbances and hyperglycemia, which are consistent with the expected toxicities of PI3K/mTOR inhibition (Lukey et al., 2019; Mercer et al., 2016). These findings highlight the therapeutic promise of PI3K/mTOR inhibitors for IPF while emphasizing the need for safer alternatives.

3.2.1 Repurposed PI3K/mTOR inhibitors

Prior to Omipalisib, Everolimus, a selective mTORc1 inhibitor, was tested in 89 IPF patients but worsened disease progression, possibly due to its partial inhibition of 4E-BP1, a key driver of TGF β 1-induced collagen production (Malouf et al., 2011; Platé et al., 2020). Newer dual mTORc1/mTORc2 inhibitors, such as Sapanisertib and Vistusertib, have shown promise in reducing TGF- β 1-induced EMT, fibrosis markers, and proinflammatory cytokines like TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 in preclinical models (Basu et al., 2018; Shaikh et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2023). Their clinical success, however, depends on balancing efficacy and safety, a challenge for PI3K/mTOR inhibitors. Current limitations of the mTOR inhibitors suggest a need for better selectivity and targeted delivery. A key question that remains unaddressed in IPF is whether isoform selective PI3K/mTOR inhibition, such as with drugs like

Alpelisib that selectively target PI3K alpha, could provide improved clinical benefits. Notably, a dual PI3K- δ/γ inhibitor, Duvelisib, indicated for Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia, was recently shown to attenuate fibrosis in vivo and in vitro (Li et al., 2023). Although these findings are clinically relevant, delivery, dosage and toxicity remain key challenges even for isoform specific inhibitors. In contrast, a new class of pan-PI3K and dual mTORc1/mTORc2 inhibitor, defined by Gedatolisib, was shown to have superior potency and efficacy over alpelisib, capivasertib (AKT inhibitor), and everolimus in breast cancer cell lines. Currently, a global combinatorial phase 3 study with Gedatolisib is underway for patients with HR+/HER2- ABC mutations (Rossetti et al., 2024). The results of this trial may inform future studies exploring the potential of pan-PI3K/dual mTOR inhibitors in the treatment of IPF.

3.2.2 Novel PI3K/mTOR Inhibitors

While drug repurposing remains a promising strategy, significant advancements have also been made in developing novel PI3K/mTOR inhibitors designed specifically for IPF pathophysiology. These drugs provide unique mechanisms of action and modes of administration, which could potentially leading to greater clinical benefits over existing drugs. Campa et al. developed KITCL27, as an inhalation-based prodrug pan-PI3K inhibitor designed to be activated only after hydrolysis inside target cells. Preclinical studies of KITCL27 in bleomycin-induced mouse models showed that inhaled CL27c effectively reduced lung fibrosis by decreasing collagen deposition and downregulated key pro-fibrotic markers, including TGF- β 1, CTGF, Collagen type I (Coll1a1), and matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP2) (Campa et al., 2018). Another innovative approach to PI3K inhibition was the development of FAPL-PI3Ki1 by Hettiarachchi et. al., which is a PI3K inhibitor conjugated to a ligand that targets fibroblast activation protein (FAP), a protein exclusively expressed by collagen-producing myofibroblasts. This FAPL-PI3Ki1 demonstrated reduced collagen deposition, decreased the expression of fibrotic markers such as α -SMA and Coll A1, and improved survival in bleomycin-induced mice (Hettiarachchi et al., 2020).

3.2.3 Akt inhibitors

Considering the ineffectiveness of existing drugs, the toxicity of PI3K inhibitors and the role of Akt hyperactivation in fibrosis progression, targeting Akt through pharmacological inhibition offers a new therapeutic approach for IPF. Given the extensive research and development that has already been conducted on Akt inhibitors for cancers, their pharmacokinetics, safety profiles, and molecular interactions are well understood, making them strong candidates for repurposing in IPF (Table 1) (Abdalla et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2022). Notably, Akt inhibitors like Triciribine and MK-2206 have already been tested in bleomycin-induced mouse models of IPF (Cui et al., 2020; Gou and Wang, 2022) supporting their use and development for IPF.

Drug Name	Original Indication	Mechanism of Action	Relevance in IPF
Triciribine (Abdalla et al., 2015)	Solid Tumors and Hematological Malignancies	ATP-competitive Akt inhibitor	In bleomycin-induced mouse models, Triciribine reduced pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6) and fibrosis markers (TGF- β , collagen I).
MK-2206 (Cui et al., 2020)	Solid Tumors including non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	Allosteric Akt inhibitor	In bleomycin-induced mouse models, MK-2206 reduced inflammatory cytokine release (TNF- α , IL-6) and decreased ECM production in fibroblasts.
Perifosine (Taniguchi et al., 2021)	Multiple Myeloma and Other Cancers	Allosteric Akt inhibitor	In radiation-induced lung injury models, Perifosine inhibited the PI3K/Akt pathway in Sox9-expressing lung epithelial cells.
Afuresertib (Yamaji et al., 2017)	Solid Tumors	ATP-competitive Akt inhibitor	Clinical evidence required to study its use in IPF

Ipatasertib (Turner et al., 2022)	Prostate Cancer, Breast Cancer	ATP-competitive Akt inhibitor	Further research needed to explore antifibrotic effects in IPF relevant models
Capivasertib (Turner et al., 2023)	Prostate Cancer, Breast Cancer	ATP-competitive inhibitor	Further research needed to explore antifibrotic effects in IPF relevant models
Uprosertib (Barnes et al., 2020)	Solid Tumours including NSCLC	ATP-competitive Akt inhibitor	Further research needed to explore antifibrotic effects in IPF relevant models, could be repurposed considering its effects in NSCLC

Table 1. Summary of Akt inhibitors used as monotherapies for cancers, with the potential for repurposing in IPF.

Similar to oral PI3K inhibitors, the development of Akt inhibitors faces challenges due to adverse effects such as diarrhoea, nausea, and skin rashes, as observed in clinical trials for solid tumors. ATP-competitive inhibitors like ipatasertib and capivasertib struggle with selectivity issues within the AGC kinase family, leading to off-target effects. In contrast, allosteric inhibitors that bind to the Pleckstrin Homology domain of Akt offer greater specificity for Akt. However, these allosteric inhibitors have shown limited clinical efficacy and require optimization before they can be considered viable options for IPF treatment.

3.2.4 Akt degraders

A novel alternative to pharmacological inhibition of Akt is to reduce intracellular Akt levels via protein degradation. This strategy has led to the development of Akt degraders, which are proteolysis targeting chimeras linked to Akt inhibitors. INY-03-041 is a pan-Akt degrader that combines GDC-0068, a pan-Akt inhibitor, with Lenalidomide, an immunomodulatory drug that recruits Cereblon (CRBN) and brings it into close proximity to Akt. CRBN acts as a substrate adaptor, guiding Akt to the E3 ubiquitin ligase complex, where Akt is tagged with ubiquitin and subsequently degraded by the proteasome (You et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2022). To date, there are only a handful of Akt degraders currently under development for solid tumours, including INY-03-041, MS21, MS143 and MS5033. Although they are yet to be repurposed for clinical studies in IPF, Akt degraders exhibit a longer half-life and a more prolonged pharmacological effect compared to their constituent Akt inhibitors alone (Yu et al., 2022), which could provide added benefits in terms of dose reduction. However, the on-target toxicities already observed with pharmacological AKT inhibitors, combined with the increased potency of AKT degraders suggest that AKT degraders may have a smaller therapeutic window. Therefore, it will be critical to explore dosages to achieve a balance between safety and efficacy for both, cancers and IPF.

3.3 Targeting other mediators along the PI3K/Akt pathway

Since the approval of Nintedanib, several tyrosine kinase inhibitors have been repurposed for IPF with mixed outcomes. Imatinib, a PDGFR and TGF- β inhibitor, was discontinued due to lack of clinical benefits (Daniels et al., 2004). Pamufetinib, a VEGFR, PDGFR, and HGFR inhibitor, showed acceptable safety in a phase 2 trial (Nishioka et al., 2023). Similar to Nintedanib, Pamufetinib also inhibits both PDGFR- α and PDGFR- β (Wollin et al., 2014), however, the targeted inhibition of PDGFR- β but not PDGFR- α attenuates fibrosis (Kishi et al., 2018) in bleomycin-treated mice. Additionally, some tyrosine kinases like VEGFR and FGFR exhibit isoform-specific, context-dependent profibrotic or antifibrotic effects which make growth factor inhibition increasingly complex.

TGF- β remains a key therapeutic target upstream of PI3K/Akt, though its inhibition poses challenges due to adverse effects, including heart valve lesions and skin cancers (Ciardiello et al., 2020; Massagué and Sheppard, 2023; Mitra et al., 2020). Indirect approaches like integrin inhibition with Bexotegrast, a dual $\alpha\beta6/\alpha\beta1$ inhibitor, have shown promise, reducing lung function decline in a phase 2 study with no severe adverse events (Lancaster et al., 2024). Longer and larger clinical trials are awaited to

conclude positive clinical outcomes. Another novel strategy to indirectly inhibit TGF- β signaling involves targeting lysyl oxidase-like 2 (LOXL2), an enzyme restricted to fibroblasts. Inhibition of LOXL2 enzymatic activity induces its auto-oxidation, leading to the creation of a metabolite that directly inhibits TGF- β receptor I (T β RI) kinase (Wei et al., 2017). Downstream of PI3K/Akt/mTOR, drugs targeting NF κ B, GSK-3 β (Rizzieri et al., 2016) and p706Sk have been developed, though not all have been tested in IPF models (Cheng et al., 2021). Specifically, ACT001, an NF κ B inhibitor, was the latest of NF κ B inhibitors that demonstrated anti-fibrotic activity in fibroblasts from IPF patients (Jaffar et al., 2021).

3.4 Senolytics in IPF

Despite the pervasive role of senescence in IPF, current standard-of-care drugs have no effect on senescence markers in IPF tissues (Zhang et al., 2019), highlighting the possibility of a more direct approach. Senolytics, a class of drugs targeting senescent cells, showed promising preclinical and early clinical trial results in IPF patients (Schafer et al., 2017). Quercetin attenuated bleomycin-induced pulmonary fibrosis, by reducing senescence markers like p21 and SASP, and inhibiting apoptosis resistance via modulating Akt activity (Hohmann et al., 2019). A first-in-human study with Quercetin and Dasatinib demonstrated selective senescent cell elimination, reduced markers, and modest functional improvement, supporting their potential as IPF therapies (Justice et al., 2019). Although, larger, randomized clinical trials are necessary to further validate this data, given that mTOR inhibitors have also directly demonstrated reduction in senescence markers, it would be interesting to evaluate the effects of more diverse “senolytic cocktails” targeting both senescence and fibrosis. Senolytics may also complement PI3K inhibitors, offering a synergistic approach to disrupt the profibrotic cycle. Furthermore, other classes of anti-senescence drugs, including SASP inhibitors and drugs targeting senescent pathways such as Navitoclax could be included in these drug cocktails to develop newer therapies. Considering that shortened telomeres are linked to higher risks of IPF, telomerase activators such as TA-65 (Tiendrébogo et al., 2023), which counteract telomere shortening linked to IPF progression could be studied in IPF, alone and in combination with inhibitors of PI3K/Akt.

4 Conclusion

IPF is a chronic, interstitial lung disease marked by significant patient heterogeneity and a lack of relevant biomarkers to guide drug development. Over the years, considerable progress has been made in understanding the mechanisms driving IPF, particularly the dysregulation of the PI3K/Akt pathway. While recent advances in selective PI3K inhibitors, Akt-specific modulators, and dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors offer promising therapeutic potential, challenges such as selectivity and systemic toxicities remain significant barriers to their clinical application. Innovative strategies, such as inhalation-based prodrugs [e.g., KITCL27 (Campa et al., 2018)] and fibroblast-specific conjugates [e.g., FAPL-PI3Ki1 (Hettiarachchi et al., 2020)], represent important steps toward reducing systemic toxicity while enhancing therapeutic efficacy. These evolving approaches underscore the need for precise, pathway-specific interventions to improve treatment outcomes in IPF.

Senescence is increasingly recognized as a key driver of IPF, with PTEN loss and PI3K/Akt hyperactivation exacerbating senescence in alveolar epithelial cells and fibroblasts, forming a feedback loop that accelerates disease progression. Senolytics, such as Dasatinib and Quercetin, offer a transformative approach by selectively eliminating senescent cells, reducing fibrosis and inflammation in preclinical studies. Addressing IPF requires a multifaceted strategy combining targeted therapies like PI3K inhibitors with interventions tackling aging-related mechanisms, including mitochondrial dysfunction and telomere attrition. Exploring such combination therapies may provide greater benefits by addressing multiple aspects of IPF pathogenesis. While current treatments remain limited, advances in targeting PI3K/Akt, senescence, and aging-related pathways offer a promising path to mitigate the impact of this devastating disease.

Conflict of Interest

EH is the co-founder and scientific advisor of Kither Biotech, a pharmaceutical company developing PI3K inhibitors for the treatment of respiratory diseases.

Author Contributions

JB wrote the manuscript. EH reviewed, edited and finalized the manuscript. All authors contributed to manuscript revision, read, and approved the submitted version.

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